

Designed by ademarco	Checked by	Approved by	Date	Date 14/11/2018
plastic non trasparent		Edition		
		Sheet 1 / 1		

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		enclosure_B1_top_1		
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			ext_mic_bracket		
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Stainless					
			ext_mic_bracket_adapter	Edition	Sheet 1 / 1

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Alu			ext_mic_bracket_mirror_bracket	
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Alu		ext_mic_bracket_stage_90deg		
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A (1:1)

B-B (1:2)

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Alu			LM_enclosure_B1		
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			LM_enclosure_B1	Edition
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Plastic non transparent or translucent			LM_enclosure_B1_top2	Edition
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Plastic non transparent or translucent			LM_enclosure_B1_top3		
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Stainless St.			LM_flange	Sheet 1 / 1

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Alu			motor_BS_dich_adapter_plate		
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Stainless St.			Obj_bracket_V2	Edition 1
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